

Deep Visual Odometry and Pose Reconstruction through Single Image Depth Map and Triangulation

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Relative navigation solutions for planetary landing in close proximity to the surface have exploited geometry-based solutions of monocular Visual Odometry (VO) due to their robustness and accuracy. However, they encounter challenges in dynamic and low-texture environments, as well as the issue of scale drift, where errors accumulate over time. Recent advancements in research indicate that deep neural networks can autonomously learn scene depths and relative camera positions without relying on ground truth labels. Despite this, their accuracy still falls short compared to traditional methods, primarily due to the absence of geometric information. A hybrid solution has shown promising results, thus, this paper proposes DepthGlue, a VO pipeline that seamlessly integrates multi-view geometry and deep learning, leveraging single-image depth estimation (SIDE) for scale consistency and a CNN feature tracker and matcher network based on the LightGlue architecture.

1 Introduction

The lunar environment has garnered increased attention from space research communities due to long-term plans of space agencies, notably activities related to the Lunar Gateway [1–4]. Recent advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) have demonstrated its utility across various space domain tasks, including navigation and formation flying guidance and navigation [5–10].

This paper presents a vision-based navigation system utilizing AI for relative navigation in lunar landing test case scenario. Different solutions have been proposed in the field. For instance, in [11] a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) coupled with a Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) network has been used to estimate the 6-DoF pose of a UAV during landing. A similar structure (CNN+LSTM) has been extended by [12] to map navigation sensor inputs directly to control actions for lunar landing maneuvers. Recurrent CNNs (RCNNs) have been used for end-to-end 6-DoF visual odometry [13], while CNNs have been

employed to estimate depth fields of scenes, with the AI output being refined by optimization algorithms [14]. While not developing the complete navigation pipeline, the study foresees the integration of VO with navigation filters and inertial sensors for accurate relative pose estimation.

1.1 Geometry and Deep Learning based Relative Navigation

Geometry-based Visual Odometry (VO) has historically performed well under specific conditions, such as static, well-textured scenes with uniform illumination. Traditional methods detect and match sparse feature points, but often face challenges like depth-translation scale ambiguity and scale drift, which require complex solutions like maintaining scale-consistent maps or global bundle adjustment [15–17]. Recently, deep learning approaches have enabled end-to-end learning of structure and motion from unlabeled frames, offering scale-consistent predictions using stereo [18–20] or monocular training [21]. These approaches provide robust scale recovery and accurate camera motion estimation, particularly when combined with techniques like RANSAC to handle outliers [22, 23]. Notable systems like ORB-SLAM2 [24] and DSO [25] exemplify this, addressing issues like scale drift and improving robustness. While traditional methods, such as feature-based [24, 26, 27] and direct methods [25, 28], remain effective, hybrid approaches leveraging deep learning have shown promise. The excellent work of DFVO [29, 30] integrates single-view depth prediction with dense optical flow matching using CNNs, enhancing VO accuracy by leveraging both deep learning and multi-view geometry.

2 Algorithm description

The *DepthGlue* algorithm pipeline features three modules mainly:

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- Single Image Depth Estimation (SIDE)
- Deep features extraction and matching
- Geometric multi-view geometry
- Scale recovery

2.1 Monocular Depth Estimation

The goal of the single-image depth prediction task is to estimate continuous values, represented as $y \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$, for each pixel in the input RGB image, $x \in [0, 255]^{3 \times H \times W}$. In this context, H and W denote the height and width of the input image, respectively. To establish 3D-2D correspondences between two views, $(\mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{p}_j)$, we need to derive the 3D structure of the i -th view and identify the correspondences between the 3D and 2D landmarks. Traditional methods achieve this by matching features between 3D landmarks and 2D feature points. In this work, we utilize a deep depth network as our "depth sensor" to estimate the 3D structure of the i -th view, X_i . Using the 2D-2D correspondences established by matching, we can directly obtain a set of 3D-2D correspondences and determine the relative camera pose by solving the PnP problem.

The preliminary results reported in the following sections implement a fine-tuned version of *Monodepth2* network [31], trained on *kitti-depth* dataset and *nyuv2* dataset.

2.2 Deep Feature Extraction & Matching

The objective of this module is to extract and match salient features in two subsequent images. The locations of the n_f matched features in the two successive camera frames ($k-1$ and k) are stored in stacked variables, \mathbf{m}_{k-1} and \mathbf{m}_k , whose columns:

- $\mathbf{m}_{k-1,i} = [u_{k-1} \ v_{k-1} \ 1]_i^T$: location of the matched feature i in camera frame at time instant $k-1$;
- $\mathbf{m}_k, i = [u_k \ v_k \ 1]_i^T$: location of the matched feature i in camera frame at time instant k .

The frame-to-frame matched features are fed to the geometrical reconstruction module that derives the camera pose for each frame by either 2D-2D correspondences or by the PnP implementation.

In this paper, *LightGlue* [32], a novel deep neural network tailored for matching local features across images is adopted. The *LightGlue* architecture explore modifications to state-of-the-art architecture that render it notably more resource-efficient in terms of both memory usage and computational load, while also enhancing its accuracy and simplifying the training

Figure 1: Feature matches.

Figure 2: Point pruning across layers with *LightGlue* implementation [32].

process. A distinguishing feature of *LightGlue* is its adaptability to the complexity of the matching task, resulting in significantly accelerated inference times for image pairs that are perceptually easier to match. Figure 1 and 2 show both the matches and the point pruning across layers. In this case, *LightGlue* prunes a few points with closed to shadowed areas, but is able to stop the context aggregation after 3 layers.

Concerning the adaptability of the matcher network to adapt to easy tasks, a brief comparative study has been performed to understand the gain in inference for this scenario, where most of the images share significant overlap and illumination. The image pairs have been taken in two different phases of the landing arc: the former is representative of the ballistic arc where the trajectory is fairly horizontal with respect to the terrain; the latter, named *brake arc* is when the lander breaks and start descending vertically towards the terrain. Figure 3 shows the results.

As shown, the adaptive version of the implementation is able to deliver optimal accuracy for the least inference time.

2.3 Epipolar Geometry and Perspective-n-Point

Relative terrain navigation relies on frame-to-frame (2D-2D) motion estimation that works with extracted

Figure 3: Latency comparison for different *LightGlue* modes.

features from a pair of images, without creating any maps of the surrounding environment. Once the features are tracked, a set of correspondences is available between the two frames.

Each of these features are related by the epipolar constraint given by Equation (1).

$$0 = \mathbf{m}_{k,i}^T \mathbf{E} \mathbf{m}_{k-1,i} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{R}[\mathbf{t}]_{\times} \quad (2)$$

in which \mathbf{R} is the rotation matrix between the camera poses in two successive frames, namely from step $k-1$ to k and \mathbf{t} is the translation between the camera origin between two successive frames, expressed in the camera frame at step k , which is equal to the body frame $\mathbf{B}_{b_1, b_2, b_3|k}$ for simplicity. With reference to reference frames in [33], one can write the epipolar constraint as: The reference frames, relevant for visual odometry, are described in Figure 4. With reference to Figure 4, one can write the epipolar constraint as:

$$\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{B}\mathbf{R}_{I,k}][\mathbf{B}\mathbf{R}_{I,k-1}]^T \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{t} = (\mathbf{r}_k - \mathbf{r}_{k-1})|_k \quad (4)$$

where it is important to note that the translation between two camera frames is expressed in the body frame $\mathbf{B}_{b_1, b_2, b_3|k}$, at time instant k .

2.4 Scale Recovery and Consistency

The scale recovery step utilises the prediction of the depth map and the triangulation of the perspective geometry solution to retrieve a scaling factor, s . The scaling factor can be estimated by aligning the triangulated depth map with the CNN depth map. For CNN depth maps, especially if not trained on the specific scenario, the absolute scale can be non-trivial to derive; nevertheless, such scale recovery ensures consistency in pose estimation and limits, or in best cases avoids, the scale drift issue, which is quite dramatic

Figure 4: Frame-to-frame visual odometry reference frames.

in traditional VO pipelines. The simple alignment between the depth value $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_i$ predicted by the CNN and the triangulated set of up-to scale depths \mathbf{d} .

3 Results

The nominal scenario that has been explored for this preliminary study represents an unseen test case trajectory that simulates the ballistic and main brake phase of a lunar lander, reproduced in a robotic arm facility with a Moon diorama [10, 34]. The *groundtruth* dataset is the calibrated trajectory reconstructed with high-resolution camera and Structure-from-Motion pipeline [35, 36]. Basically, the trajectory is performed using a robotic-arm facility with a Moon diorama [34], the pose of each point is retrieved by using dense point cloud reconstruction and pose estimation in a Structure-from-Motion framework (i.e. COLMAP). This was done to actually compare an accurate but computationally expensive camera-only method with the proposed one.

The first step of *DepthGlue* pipeline is the single frame depth estimation that for each pixel assigns a depth value $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_i$ that is used for a twofold objective:

- scale recovery for those pairs that deliver a consistent Epipolar reconstruction and a triangulated set of points \mathbf{d} . A scaling factor, s , can be estimated by aligning the triangulated depth map with the CNN depth map.
- 2D-3D correspondence for PnP pipeline.

An example of 2D-3D correspondence is shown in Fig. 5. The depth map is critical to recover the scale and enhance the traditional visual odometry, as successfully demonstrated in [29]. The single-frame

Figure 5: Depth map feature matching for 2D-3D correspondences.

Figure 6: CNN depth recovery for a trajectory frame of the lunar terrain.

depth, shown in Fig. 6, demonstrates that even with general-purpose training, the depth recovery is capable of reconstructing the scene. The numerical results of the reconstructed trajectory is shown in Fig. 7 and 8. Calculating the root mean squared error of the prediction:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_{p,i} - X_{gt,i})^2} \quad (5)$$

we get a the following results:

- Position RMSE: 0.56 m
- Attitude RMSE: 0.12 rad

The execution times are reported in Tab. 1. In-depth investigations of numerical results demonstrate that the longest calculation is the feature extraction and matching step, which is quite demanding also in classical pipelines. The algorithm has been run using a *GPU Nvidia GeForce RTX 3050 Mobile*. Although not representative of embedded systems, the computational times are deemed to be acceptable at this very early prototyping phase. Indeed, the code is run in *python* and the networks architectures are not optimized for deployment. Hence, it is expected that an

embedded application, properly deployed in *C/C++* and distilled/optimized network models, may be able to meet typical on-board computational times requirements.

Deep inference	Time (s)
Monodepth2	0.018
Lightglue	0.179
Perspective	Time (s)
Ess. mat track	0.024
Scale recovery	0.080

Table 1: Timing metrics for the different modules and their respective tasks.

4 Discussion

The work presented in the paper consist of a robust yet simple relative navigation Visual Odometry system that integrates multi-view geometry and deep learning, from which the name *DepthGlue* visual odometry, on depth and deep matching, making use of single image depth estimation and of a feature tracker and matcher network built on the *LightGlue* architecture. The networks have been trained using general purpose datasets and deployed against the unseen scenario of Moon landing. Typically space-based applications require training on representative datasets, which has not been exploited in this work mainly for one reason: the availability of a proper dataset. The possibility to include representative datasets can significantly improve the accuracy of the method, as the fractal nature of Moon terrain is inherently a hard challenge for depth reconstruction.

The direct comparison of the proposed method with integrated VO pipeline used in planetary landing is not beneficial, as these are typically part of larger systems integrating multiple sensors and estimation techniques. The idea is that the proposed method could be part of one of those. For instance, the method may directly feed a filter with state estimate or, on the other hand, the VO pipeline could benefit from attitude estimation. Indeed, in many spacecraft navigation applications there is no need for an image-based terrain relative navigation system to explicitly estimate full pose from image data alone. This is particularly the case when excellent attitude knowledge is available from star trackers, IMUs, and other attitude sensors [37]. However, the challenges for a proper comparison in multiple scenario with state of the art literature

Figure 7: Top: position comparison for each timestamp. Mid: planar projection of 3D trajectory. Bottom: attitude pose reconstruction.

Figure 8: 3D comparison of groundtruth and reconstructed trajectory in world reference frame.

methods lies on the lack of standardized dataset for image based relative terrain navigation.

The preliminary results demonstrated promising outcome on the generalization capability and consistent reconstruction. The immediate work that is being carried out is focused on:

- transfer learning of trained network using fine-tuned depth datasets of lunar landing. Obviously, the availability of depth datasets for such scenario is very limited, thus it is quite challenging to fulfill this task reliably. Most likely, synthetic imageries will be used;
- investigating the single-frame depth estimation with diffusion-based models [38];
- thorough testing on multiple trajectories involving remarkable illumination differences and attitude maneuvers.

Overall, despite the accuracy has still considerable margin to be explored, the method is deemed to be a promising pipeline for enhancing relative navigation with only optical camera as sensor, reconstructing depths by deep learning techniques.

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